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UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF TERIFLUNOMIDE IN TABLET

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ABSTRACT

Teriflunomide is the active metabolite of leflunomide. It is an immunomodulatory agent used in the treatment of multiple sclerosis. UV spectrophotometric method has been developed for the estimation of teriflunomide in tablets using methanol as solvent. Teriflunomide has shown λ_{max} at 293 nm. The method has been validated according to ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines. A linear response is observed ($R^2=0.9995$) in the range of 4-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, with recovery (100.68%) and precision (% RSD is 0.07). This method is simple and suitable for routine pharmaceutical analysis.

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INTRODUCTION

Teriflunomide [(Z)-2-cyano-3-hydroxy-N-[4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]but-2-enamide)] is a novel immune-suppressive/immune modulatory agent (Fig. 1). Teriflunomide (TEF) is the active metabolite of leflunomide[1]. It is useful in the treatment of multiple sclerosis. Multiple Sclerosis is a demyelinating disorder that affects the central nervous system. The immune system attacks the myelin sheath of the nerve fiber, causing inflammation, which destroys nerve cell processes, altering electrical messages in the brain. TEF acts by inhibiting pyrimidine de novo synthesis by blocking the enzyme dihydroorotate dehydrogenase, an enzyme involved in the synthesis of pyrimidine. The drug was approved by the USFDA and EMA[2].

Fig.1 Teriflunomide.

A literature survey reveals that only a single method is reported for teriflunomide by UV spectrophotometry in acetonitrile at 284nm[3]. Some other methods are also reported such as LC-UV[4-12], LC-MS[12], LC-MS/MS[13], HPTLC[14-15]. So, there is a need for a UV spectrophotometric method using methanol for the estimation of teriflunomide in the tablet formulation. Therefore, the current work is to develop a validated simple, and precise UV spectrophotometric method for the estimation of teriflunomide in tablet formulation.

Materials and method

Instruments

UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer (Systronics-2201), Electronic balance (Shimadzu AY220) were used.

Materials

Teriflunomide was obtained from Biocon Ltd., Bangalore, as a gift sample. Methanol was obtained from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. Denopsy tablet containing 14mg (Natco Pharma Ltd.) purchased locally.

Methods

Selection of solvent

Solubility of TEF was checked in different solvents like methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, and distilled water.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution

10mg of teriflunomide was transferred to a 10ml volume tri-cl flask, dissolved in methanol, and volume was made up to the mark with methanol to get 1000µg/ml solution. 0.8ml of the above solution was diluted to 20ml with methanol (40µg/ml).

Determination of Absorption Maxima

Teriflunomide solution (16µg/ml) was scanned in the range of 200-400nm in UV-VIS Spectrophotometer to determine the absorption maxima.

Preparation of Sample Solution

10 tablets were weighed and powdered. Powder equivalent to 70mg teriflunomide was weighed and transferred to a 50ml volume tri-cl flask, dissolved in methanol, and volume was made up to the mark with methanol (1400µg/ml). This solution was sonicated and filtered using Whatman filter paper. 1ml of filtrate was diluted to 10ml to get 140µg/ml solution, and 1ml of the resulting solution was diluted to 10ml with methanol to get a final concentration of 14µg/ml and the absorbance of the solution was measured at 293nm.

Method Validation

Validation of the method was carried out as per the ICH guidelines [16] for the following parameters.

Linearity and Range

The concentration of 4, 8, 12, 16, and 20µg/ml of teriflunomide solutions were prepared by diluting a standard stock solution of 40µg/ml with methanol. The absorbance of these solutions was recorded at 293 nm. The graph was plotted between absorbance and concentration. The correlation coefficient of TEF was calculated.

Precision

The precision of an analytical procedure is defined as the closeness of agreement between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions.

The absorbance of teriflunomide solutions (16 µg/ml) was determined and the same was repeated six times on the same day (repeatability) and three consecutive days (intermediate precision).

Accuracy

Accuracy of the developed method was carried out by performing a recovery study using the standard addition method, in which the standard drug was spiked at three different levels (80%, 100%, and 120%) to the pre-analyzed formulation. The amount of TEF was calculated at each level and % recoveries were calculated.

$$\% \text{ Recovery} = \frac{\text{recovered value}}{\text{spiked value}} \times 100$$

Robustness

The robustness of the developed method is its capacity to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters. The robustness of the method was determined by measuring the absorbance of 16 µg/ml TEF solution at 292nm, 293nm, and 291nm i.e., ± 1nm.

Results and Discussion

Selection of solvent

Teriflunomide is soluble in water, and soluble in methanol and acetonitrile. Methanol is selected as the solvent.

Determination of Absorption Maxima

The teriflunomide solution (16 µg/ml) showed λ_{max} 293nm (Fig. 2).

Fig.2 UV spectrum of teriflunomide.

Method Validation

Linearity and Range

Linearity concentrations and absorbances are displayed in (Table 1). Absorbance v/s concentration of TEF graph is plotted (Fig. 3). The method is linear over the range 4-20 µg/ml with correlation coefficient of 0.9995 and regression equation as $y=0.0578x+0.141$. The overlay of UV spectra is shown in (Fig. 4).

Table: 1 Linearity.

Conc.(µg/ml)	Absorbance
4	0.375
8	0.597
12	0.832
16	1.079
20	1.29

Fig. 3 Calibration curve of teriflunomide

Fig.4 Overlay of UV spectra of 4-20µg/ml of TEF.

Precision

The absorbance of six experiments and % RSD (< 2) for repeatability and intermediate precision is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Results of repeatability and intermediate precision.

Sr. No.	Absorbance (Repeatability)	Absorbance (Intermediate precision)		
		Day1	Day2	Day3
1	1.101	1.109	1.16	1.173
2	1.100	1.11	1.157	1.173
3	1.099	1.11	1.157	1.170
4	1.1	1.113	1.157	1.148
5	1.1	1.111	1.158	1.144
6	1.101	1.108	1.157	1.144
Mean	1.10	1.11	1.16	1.15
SD	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.015
%RSD	0.09	0.18	0.09	1.30

Accuracy

Accuracy is between 100.12-101.71% as shown in table 3.

Table 3 Results of recovery.

Sr.No.	Level of % Recovery	Amount Added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery
1.	80	6.4	6.51	101.71
2.	100	8.0	8.01	100.12
3.	120	9.6	9.62	100.20

Robustness

The robustness of the method was studied by calculating % the relative standard deviation, it was found to be less than 2% (Table 4). The variation in the wave length showed similar results.

Table 4 Robustness.

Sr. no.	Wavelength (nm)	Absorbance	Mean \pm SD	%RSD
1.	292	1.119		
2.	293	1.113	1.112 \pm 0.007	0.629
3.	294	1.105		

Assay of Teriflunomide Tablet

The developed method is applied for the estimation of TEF in the tablet. The result of the assay is shown in (Table 5). Teriflunomide tablet contains 101.71 % of the stated amount of Teriflunomide $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{F}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$.

Table 5 TEF content in tablet.

Formulation	Drug	Label claim (mg)	Amount of drug found (mg)	% Content
DENOPSY	Teriflunomide	14	14.24	101.71

CONCLUSION

The simple, cost-effective UV spectrophotometric method is developed and validated in compliance with ICH guidelines for the estimation of teriflunomide. This method is accurate, precise, sensitive and linear in the range of 4-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The analytical method can be used for routine analysis of teriflunomide in the formulation in quality control, research, and analytical laboratories.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no Conflict of interest.

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